

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NCHAPI-MOLOISANE****FIRST NAME: LUCY****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: P1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with the page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Introduction
2. A step-by-step process of academic essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 7 – 9; 11)
3. The structure of academic essays (EUCLID 2021, 10 – 12)
4. The language variations between American and British English and rules of academic writing (EUCLID 2021, 13 – 32)
5. Styles in academic essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 40 – 56)
6. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33 - 39)
7. Conclusion

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I have read through the ACA-401D course material and reviewed the content. The detailed course description clarifies the expectations of what I need to do to achieve the learning outcomes.

EUCLID's approach to providing this comprehensive information better prepares me for the learning process I am undertaking. I clearly understand how to communicate ideas based on evidence in scholarly writing. A step-by-step approach is commendable and provides a logical flow that is easy to follow. I have been apprehensive about writing a response paper; however, the resources and guidance have eased my anxieties.

In this response paper, I discuss how academic essay is structured and the process of academic writing. The language between American and British English is analyzed. I will explore the significance of the styles in academic writing and how to avoid plagiarism.

2) A STEP-BY-STEP PROCESS OF ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

This section outlines the process of academic writing step by step. Academic writing is a formal style of essay writing required in scholarly writing. Academic essay writing is a process that provides a piece of clear, concise, focused and well-structured evidence (Yarris et al. 2020, 1- 6). The evidence is derived from research obtained through literature searches from published journals, periodicals, reports, books, and unpublished fieldwork, for example. The aim is to provide answers to research questions.

EUCLID (2021, 8) described the basic eleven steps in writing an essay in a hierarchical version that is simple and easy to follow. The structure provides a flexible guide, not a bureaucratic control. The first step is seeking knowledge and understanding of the topic by researching the evidence using credible academic sources. It is crucial to establish what is already known to explore the unknown. The use of reading lists and creditable databases is significant. It is necessary to analyze the resources and their relevance to the topic. The analysis involves critical thinking. Critical thinking is the ability to read and succinctly evaluate the evidence to identify strengths and weaknesses and exclude bias (Borglin 2012, 612). Creativity is another crucial element of academic writing that uses imagination to make writing exciting and compelling. The imaginative approach involves using inner emotions, thinking processes, values and beliefs (Milicevic et al. 2020, 2).

The next step is to outline the essay plan and organize thoughts after establishing the point of view. Structure the draft into three parts: introduction, body, and conclusion for clarity EUCLID (2021, 10). The next step will discuss the structure of an academic essay. The information gathered should be aligned with the question to establish links and find answers (EUCLID 2021, 9). EUCLID (2021, 11) recommends starting the writing early, planning and structuring the work, referring to the question when developing the draft, revising the draft, and proofreading to produce a credible academic essay.

3) THE STRUCTURE OF ACADEMIC ESSAYS

The structure offers an essential guide for academic essays and presents the writer's ideas and thoughts. EUCLID (2021, 10) recommends a format that includes an introduction, body, and conclusion. The introduction opens with a short orientation of the topic and provides a brief background of the essay, highlighting the main ideas. It is vital to give an overview of the organization of sections to create anticipation and clarity.

The body section discusses the main ideas of the academic essay using paragraphs. EUCLID (2021, 10) suggests that paragraphs should build on each other and show a link demonstrating a logical flow of ideas and arguments. The use of relevant examples and supporting evidence is recommended. It is crucial to critically interpret the evidence highlighting the meaning and connotations and making sense of any associated impact. The

discussion should focus on providing the answer to the question. In cases where there are more aspects to the questions, the use of subsections is advised.

The conclusion restated the answer to the question, the summary of the main points, and the final statement regarding future directions (EUCLID 2021, 10).

Referencing the essay is essential in academic writing, and schools use different styles (EUCLID 2021, 12).

The following section will discuss the rules of thumb for writing a paper and the language variations between American and British English.

4) THE LANGUAGE VARIATIONS BETWEEN AMERICAN AND BRITISH ENGLISH AND RULES OF ACADEMIC WRITING

EUCLID (2021, 12) suggests rules of thumb for writing a paper, such as stating the paper's main thesis at the beginning, staying focused by incorporating a theory and demonstrating the relevance to the topic or issue being addressed in the academic essay. Writing should be clear, and views supported by evidence. EUCLID (2021, 13) advocates for a stylistic variety, such as avoiding passive constructions and long strings of prepositional clauses to make the writing enjoyable. When analyzing the relevant parts of the philosopher's views, it is essential to consider how the philosopher would respond to the criticism (EUCLID 2021, 14).

Punctuations are essential to convey meanings to sentences (EUCLID 2021, 16). For example, a hyphen could be used in an adjectival phrase before a noun. Apostrophes are used to indicate possession after singular nouns. Use a colon to introduce a subclause following the text before it and a pair of commas surrounding a non-defining clause. Single quotation marks are used for direct speech, while double quotation marks are for direct address (EUCLID 2021, 16 – 23).

Academic writing needs to be meaningful and consistent; EUCLID (2021, 25) recommends using a specific variant of the English language. EUCLID (2021, 25) states that American English is more predominantly used globally than British English. The reasons attributed to the high use of American English include the wealth of the US economy, the magnitude of higher education in America versus the United Kingdom, technological media influence and the international political position of the US.

EUCLID (2021, 25) identified similarities and differences between American and British English, such as words with different pronunciations but exact spelling. Some comments have different spelling but the same pronunciation, while others have similar spelling and pronunciation. Observing the differences and similarities is pivotal to avoiding confusion and conveying a precise meaning when writing.

5) **STYLES IN ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING**

Style guides describe a format for documenting academic essays and provide rules to enforce consistency (EUCLID 2021, 41). Style guides may come as templates outlining the structure, page layout, heading formats, and font styles recommended by an organization to attain consistency (EUCLID 2021, 41).

Sword (2012, 23) recommends six key points of style, such as striving to produce a precise, coherent, concise sentence, keeping sentences short and straightforward, and using plain English. Avoiding vagueness, using active rather than passive verbs, and being creative in telling a story. These recommendations are consistent with the guidelines proposed by EUCLID (2021) on academic essay writing.

I have used the Vancouver style guide for writing academic essays in the past. I found the writing style easy to use as the citation is a number given in a bracket or as a superscript. The references are listed at the end in the order they are cited in the text (Day 2013, 133-134). However, the disadvantage of numerical referencing is that the reader must refer to the reference list to identify the author and date of the source (Day 2013, 135).

EUCLID has provided a detailed explanation of Chicago and the "Turabian Style", which clarified that both styles are the same. Turabian Style is the official guide to applying Chicago Style to papers, theses, and dissertations (EUCLID 2021, 50). The Chicago style uses italics, quotation marks, abbreviations, numbers, compound words, headings, footnotes, and bibliographies (EUCLID 2021, 44-57). The Turabian is the style adopted for writing this response paper.

6) **PLAGIARISM**

In academic writing, writers must acknowledge the source of information cited. The authors who present someone's work as their own without giving credit to the original carry out plagiarism (Holland and Watson 2012, 204). It is essential to acknowledge using quotes, paraphrases, and statistical data from another source (EUCLID 2021, 34).

Plagiarism is misconduct and a breach of academic ethics (Pecorari and Shaw 2018, 7). It is vital to value academic integrity as plagiarism undermines trust and deters honest researchers (Bretag 2016, 896). EUCLID (2021, 34) highly recommends in-text citations and a reference list of the author that has provided the information as key to academic integrity.

7) **CONCLUSION**

Students must understand the rules and processes that guide academic essay writing and adhere to the required standards. Plagiarism is against the ethical standards of academic writing. Citing and referencing are fundamental to academic integrity. Following

recommended style guides and considering punctuations and the variation in the English language is pivotal to academic writing.

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